

Screening Practice of Major Congenital Malformation and Associated Factors Among Healthcare Professionals in Ethiopia: A Multi-center Cross-sectional study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Congenital anomalies are structural, functional, and metabolic abnormalities that occur during the formation of organs, which appear at birth or are discovered later in life, and can be minor or major. Major malformations are structural changes that have serious medical, surgical, social, or cosmetic consequences and necessitate medical intervention because they can lead to severe morbidity and mortality. Early diagnosis and treatment of these conditions have been shown in many cases to reduce morbidity, premature death, mental retardation, and other developmental disabilities. Early detection, particularly through newborn screening, plays a pivotal role, especially in resource constrained settings where treatment can be costly. Therefore, the study aimed to assess healthcare professionals' (HCPs) practice on screening of major congenital anomalies and associated factors among newborn infants at three tertiary government hospitals with pediatric surgical services in Ethiopia.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from November 2022 to September 2023 among 163 HCPs working at labor and delivery ward and neonatal intensive care units of Tikur Anbessa Specialized hospital, St. Paul Hospital Millennium Medical College and Menilik II comprehensive specialized hospital. Data was collected using a pre-tested standardized questionnaire adopted from WHO and CDC guidelines. Descriptive statistics were reported as frequency with percentages. To identify factors associated with practice of screening, a binary logistic regression analysis was run at 5% level of significance where adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% CIs were used to interpret significant results.

Results: Majority of HCPs have moderate to adequate knowledge (74.2%) and favorable attitude (69.3%) but only 11% demonstrated good practice on screening of major congenital anomalies. Factors significantly associated with improved screening practices included adequate knowledge of screening protocols, delivery of a female neonate, and the presence of pregnancy complications.

Conclusions: Screening practices of HCPs for major congenital malformations fall significantly below the WHO recommendations. This suggests inadequate early diagnosis and management, potentially leading to preventable mortality, morbidity, and disability associated with these conditions. To improve the practice, it is essential to expand HCPs' knowledge through staff training and experience sharing, adopting appropriate protocols and guidelines, and ensuring preparation for the applicability of these protocols and guidelines

Key words: Congenital malformation, Neonatal screening, knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Ethiopia

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